

FACTORS AFFECTING THE INTENTION TO USE E-WALLETS AMONG WORKING AGE PEOPLE IN COLOMBO DISTRICT

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Introduction

The current world is getting digitalized with many sophisticated technologies. These technological improvements have made it vital for today's consumers to rely on mobile devices as they are easier and more convenient (Nag and Gilitwala,2019). Thus, mobile payments have surpassed primitive payment methods (Nag and Gilitwala,2019).

A digital wallet/e-wallet is an application that allows users to store money and make payments digitally using e-devices like mobile phones. According to Taheam, Sharma and Goswami (2016), e-wallets have become a convenient way of making digital payments as smartphones have become an inseparable part of life and as e-wallets have progressed to be included as a payment alternative by many e-businesses. The “intention to use”, which falls under the “behavioral intention” topic, is used to test individual behaviors (Yuchen, Ronghua and Chen,2020), and it is identified to be the best factor in predicting correct behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen (1975) as cited in Karim et al.,2020).

Globally, much research have been done to study this intention to use e-wallets with its growth. Dang et al. (2019) have indicated that Sweden is in the process of going completely cashless, and some others have disallowed cash transactions above certain limits. Some researchers claim that e-wallet usage has not reached its potential due to reasons like low acceptance, unawareness, low internet connectivity, suspicion, overdependence on

physical money (Dang et al.,2019), security and fraud risks (Andrew, Ambad and Tan,2019). At the same time, Manikandan and Jayakodi (2017) claimed that with reduced risk factors, convenience and ease of use would cause tremendous growth in e-wallet usage. However, this is still in doubt when it comes to the local context.

In Sri Lanka, computer and digital literacy is 30.8% and 46.0%, in urban areas, 43.6% and 61.7%, respectively (Department of Census and Statistics,2019), and with 149% (31.80 million connections among 21.37 million population) mobile connections and 47% internet users (DATAREPORTAL,2020). Many people prefer the use of e-wallets due to other benefits like convenience, ease of use and straightforwardness during purchases in busy lifestyles, reward benefits, etc., while some might not. Thereby it points to the importance of identifying the factors affecting the use of e-wallets.

In previous studies, many factors that affect the intention to use e-wallets have been identified. The factors; perceived ease of use (PEOU), perceived usefulness (PU), subjective norms (SN), perceived trust (PT), and perceived security (PS) were identified as factors which have a significant influence on the intention to use e-wallets (Ying et al.,2019; Nag and Gilitwala,2019). But PHAN, HO and LE-HOANG (2020) concluded; that social influence and effort expectancy are vital factors as youngsters do not care about security and privacy nor the usage easiness. The study of Gupta and Arora (2019) indicated habit as the most persuasive predictor and suggested that the daily usage of smartphones in almost every task has become a habit of using it to make transactions as well.

Though many factors have been identified with regard to the usage intention of e-wallets, the findings are contradictory, and no relevant studies have been conducted locally. This study fills this gap by determining the factors affecting the intention to use e-wallets among working-age people in the

Colombo district and identifying the relationship between those factors and the intention to use e-wallets.

The findings of this study will be important for service-providing organizations to know these factors to get a better understanding of how to market and increase e-wallet adoption. The findings will also provide guidance on customer needs/preferences in using e-wallets for those involved in designing and creating to deliver an efficient e-wallet application. Further, this will contribute information to the government, which can be used to formulate relevant laws/regulations/policies related to e-wallet usage to enhance security.

Methodology

The conceptual model is developed based on the model of Ying et al. (2019), including the relationship between PU and PEOU (Trivedi,2016). This study will clearly depict how these variables impact on usage intention of e-wallets.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Six hypotheses were formulated to meet the research objective. The study took a quantitative approach using a cross-sectional survey developed using google forms. The survey was distributed via social networks explaining the purpose of the survey and the URL link to the questionnaire. The population considered was working-age people in the Colombo district, and for the representative sample, working-age people in the Colombo district who use e-wallets were selected using the convenience sampling technique.

According to the Department of Census and Statistics (2020), people of age 15 and above are considered working age people, but those below 18 were neglected as one should be of age 18 or above to use e-wallets. The sample size was calculated using Daniel Sopher's model. Thus, 161 respondents were identified as a statistically significant sample.

In data analysis, SPSS was used to analyze the descriptive statistics and SmartPLS to analyze the inferential data. The model testing was performed after checking the reliability and validity of the collected data.

Results and Discussion

Demographic profile of the respondents explains that the majority of respondents were males and 55.2% were between age 24 and 29. The employed rate was 54.5% and FriMi was the most popular e-wallet among respondents. Further, it revealed that many respondents used more than one e-wallet.

Figure 2: Types of e-wallets used

The duration of usage varied, with a majority of 41.2% using e-wallets for less than six months. And 57% used it 1-3 times per month while only 18.2% used it more than five times.

Figure 3: Duration of use

The constructs' reliability and validity were evaluated prior to model testing. The composite reliability of 0.7 or above indicates that the construct produces equivalent outcomes in the same conditions. The average variance extracted (AVE) is used to measure the convergent validity and a value of 0.5 or above reflects the convergence of questions used to assess the model's constructs. Then discriminant validity was examined using the variance extracted value. The square roots of AVE are compared with correlations between the constructs and should exceed other correlation values among the latent variables (Fornell and Larcker, 2012). The validity analysis confirmed that the variables are acceptable without any modifications.

The hypotheses results are displayed in the table below. The significant level of the calculated values is 95%.

Table 1: Significance testing result of the conceptual model

Hypothesis	Path	Path Coefficient	T-Statistics	Result
H1	Perceived usefulness is positively related with intention to use e-wallets	0.327	4.001*	Supported
H2	Perceived ease of use is positively related with the intention to use e-wallets	0.235	2.627*	Supported
H3	Perceived ease of use is positively related with perceived usefulness	0.716	11.876*	Supported
H4	Subjective norms is positively related with intention to use e-wallets	0.084	1.499	Not Supported
H5	Perceived trust is positively related with intention to use e-wallets	0.191	2.369*	Supported
H6	Perceived security is positively related with intention to use e-wallets	0.140	2.060*	Supported

Note: * p<0.05

Conclusion

The findings revealed four hypotheses to be supported and thus suggested; that when users believe that e-wallets enhance their tasks, it increases their intention towards using e-wallets(H1). When it is not complicated(H2) and is secure(H6), usage becomes satisfactory, and thus it increases; a positive belief occurs when transaction data are not revealed to external parties(H5). Furthermore, a positive relationship between perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness suggests that when an e-payment system is beneficial to the user and easy to use, usage increases. However, social norms were identified to be non-significant. The result will have been different if a sample is selected from a different area because the Colombo district is enriched with many facilities, which would facilitate the use of e-wallets more easily. The model predictability would have increased with factors like rewards, which drive the usage of new things in developing countries like Sri Lanka. However, these findings are believed to be important to e-wallet providers in Sri Lanka.

References

Andrew, J. V., Ambad, A. S. N. and Tan, K. E. (2019) 'A Model of Factors Influencing Consumers' Intention to Use e-Wallet System in Malaysia: A Systematic Review', *Malaysian Journal of Business and Economics (MJBE)*, 6(2), pp. 2289–8018.

Dang, t. *Et al.* (2019) 'Adoption of e-wallets for financial transactions : an analysis of received : 29 mar 2019 abstract accepted : 09 apr 2019', 7(4), pp. 143–154.

Datareportal (2020) *digital-2020-sri-lanka-january-2020-v01-1-638*.

Department of Census and and Statistics (2019) *Computer literacy statistics 2019 (annual)*. Available at:

<http://www.statistics.gov.lk/ComputerLiterarcy/BuletinComputerLiteracy.pdf>.

Department of Census and Statistics, S. L. (2020) *Sri Lanka Labour Force Survey 1st Quarter - 2020, Sri Lanka Labour Force Survey 1st Quarter - 2020*. Available at:

http://www.statistics.gov.lk/Resource/en/LabourForce/Bulletins/LFS_Q1_Bulletin_2020.

Fornell, C. and Larcker, D. (2012) ‘Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error’, *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), p. 32.

Gupta, K. and Arora, N. (2019) ‘Investigating consumer intention to accept mobile payment systems through unified theory of acceptance model An Indian perspective’, *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 9(2016), pp. 88–114. doi: 10.1108/SAJBS-03-2019-0037.

Karim, W. *et al.* (2020) ‘Factors Influencing the Use of E-wallet as a Payment Method among Malaysian Young Adults’, *Journal of International Business and Management*, 3(2), pp. 1–11.

Manikandan, S. and Jayakodi, J. M. (2017) ‘An Emprical Study on Consumers Adoption of Mobile Wallet With Special Reference To Chennai City’, *International Journal of Research -GRANTHAALAYAH*, 5(5), pp. 107–115. doi:10.29121/granthaalayah.v5.i5.2017.1843.

Nag, A. K. and Gilitwala, B. (2019) ‘E-Wallet- Factors Affecting Its Intention to Use’, *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(4), pp. 3411–3415. doi: 10.35940/ijrte.d6756.118419.

PHAN, T. N., HO, T. V. and LE-HOANG, P. V. (2020) ‘Factors Affecting the Behavioral Intention and Behavior of Using E-Wallets of Youth in

Vietnam’, *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(10), pp. 295–302. doi: 10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.n10.295.

Taheam, K., Sharma, R. and Goswami, S. (2016) ‘Drivers of digital wallet usage: Implications for leveraging digital marketing’, *International Journal of Economic Research*, 13(1), pp. 175–186.

Trivedi, J. (2016) ‘Factors determining the acceptance of e-wallet’, *Journal of Applied Marketing and Management*, 1(2), pp. 42–53. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Jay_Trivedi3/publication/312198449_Trivedi_J2016Factors_Determining_the_Acceptance_of_E_Wallets_International_Journal_of_Applied_Marketing_and_ManagementVol1_2pp-42-53/links/58ac2194aca27206d9bf922b/Trivedi-J2016Factor.

Ying, N. *et al.* (2019) ‘The Next Wave: Popularity of E-wallet’, (August).

Yuchen, G., Ronghua, Q. and Chen, Y. S. (2020) ‘Determinants of Intention to Use the Mobile Payment Apps among Malaysian Users’, *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)*, 22(5), pp. 64–70. doi: 10.9790/487X-2205086470.